

**THE PROBLEM OF INFORMATIVITY IN ENGLISH
FICTIONAL TEXT**

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Abstract: This article is aimed at investigating the category of informativity within the realm of English fictional texts. The study aims to explore the types and levels of informational content present in English fictional texts and examine the mechanisms through which these narratives convey information to readers and society at large. The variety of information expressed in the text is analyzed, as well as the significance of stylistic devices and pragmatic aspects for creating an aesthetic experience and emotional impact on the audience. The result of the study emphasizes the importance of understanding and analyzing stylistic and pragmatic types of information content in the context of fictional texts in order to fully understand their goals and effect on the reader.

Keywords: informativity, English fiction, stylistic information, pragmatic information.

Introduction.

The field of text linguistics is increasingly focusing on text-forming categories. By examining these categories, we gain insight into their development and function, identify their core characteristics, and discover patterns in how texts are structured and convey meaning.

One such crucial category is informativity, a complex linguistic phenomenon that has attracted the attention of numerous Russian and foreign researchers. Their diverse approaches to studying informativity have solidified its position as a fundamental text-forming category.

This article aims to delve into the multifaceted nature of this informativity, examining the ways in which fictional texts impart knowledge. By investigating the interplay between narrative structure, linguistic devices, and cognitive reception, this study seeks to unravel the informational richness inherent in English fictional texts.

Literature review.

Linguistic philosophers, linguists, and narrative studies experts have expressed a great deal of interest in investigating the category of informativity in works of fiction. Many theoretical vantage points, including those from the theory of reader response aesthetics, cognitive psychology, and narrative theory, have impacted the exploration of informativity in fictional texts. A well-known researcher in linguistics studying narrative structures was Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin who has shown how focalization, narrative viewpoint, and narrative discourse influence how readers interpret a text. Yuri Mikhailovich Lotman conducted detailed textual analysis of literary works, considering how texts operate as information-rich structures that communicate complex messages to readers. He explored how texts generate meaning through the manipulation of signs and symbols. Ilya Romanovich Galperin discusses the concept of informativity as a key aspect of textual structure and examines how writers use linguistic means to convey information and influence readers' perceptions. Specifically, he provided valuable insights into how fictional texts function as information-bearing structures that communicate meaning through linguistic and stylistic means. His investigation contributed to the understanding of how writers craft their messages and engage readers through the strategic use of language and stylistic devices, such as imagery, figures of speech, and narrative techniques. Another finding which was revealed by Viktor Vladimirovich Vinogradov contains detailed textual analyses of literary works, examining how language is used to convey meaning, evoke emotions, and create aesthetic effects in texts. V. V. Vinogradov studied the linguistic strategies employed by writers to achieve specific literary goals and his works have had a lasting impact on the field of linguistics. Ellen F. Prince investigated the concept of given/new information and developed a taxonomy to categorize information based

on its familiarity or salience in discourse. Additionally, she is associated with the theory of radical pragmatics, which challenges traditional approaches to linguistic analysis by emphasizing the importance of context, speaker intentions, and social factors in interpreting meaning. The investigation of informativity in written fiction is an area of rich complexity that requires further scholarly attention and investigation due to its variety of conceptual, aesthetic, and cognitive facets. Although the current research on the category of informativity in fictional texts has provided valuable insights into the textual, stylistic, and cognitive aspects of this phenomenon, there are still opportunities for additional exploration and interdisciplinary collaboration in this field.

Research Method and Process

This research was conducted using a traditional method approach, combining qualitative analysis of English fictional texts with a complex methodology that integrates literary analysis, stylistic examination, and pragmatic science. Several English fictional texts were selected with the focus on analyzing the types of the information they contain and exploring narrative techniques as well as identifying the readers' responses. The stylistic and pragmatic types of information that can be found in English fictional texts were analyzed. Apart from it, tools of textual analysis are used in order to investigate levels of information present. Stylistic and pragmatic frameworks aid in interpreting the strategies authors employ to enhance informativity and engage readers effectively. By considering the cognitive processes, pragmatic science uncovers the dynamics that govern how readers interpret, respond to, and derive meaning from fictional narratives.

The data for analysis was gathered from 2 English fictional works namely Charles Dickens's novel “A Tale of Two Cities”, and “Moby Dick” by Herman Melville. Only the fragments containing the types of informativity mentioned above were investigated. After carrying out the analysis, a general review of the process of analysis was put into words. The main rationale for examining this phenomenon using the mentioned methods was to guarantee the precision and reliability of the investigation.

Data analysis.

1. Stylistic information

Stylistic information for a fictional text is fundamental. (Ashurova, 2016) It manifests itself through the categories of imagery, emotiveness, evaluativeness, expressiveness, implicitness and associativity. These categories are expressed primarily using linguistic means and stylistic devices, but are not limited to them. Portraits and descriptions of landscapes perform an important function in the text, since they help to emotionally and evaluatively characterize the characters and reveal their internal emotional state.

In fictional texts, stylistic information is primarily conveyed through various mechanisms of linguistic creativity. Linguistic creativity is a cognitive activity of a language personality, aimed at the creative use of linguistic means and the creation of new words and it involves the active and original application of linguistic possibilities.

The diversity of types of linguistic creativity used in a fictional text allows us to conclude that such a text, as a result of the author's creative thinking, is one of the key forms of linguistic creativity. D. U. Ashurova states that in terms of linguistic representation of stylistic information, stylistic devices, particularly their convergence, play a dominant role and can be seen as an expression of the author's linguistic creativity. The convergence of stylistic devices also serves as a method of cognitive-stylistic highlighting, aimed at emphasizing the stylistic potential of linguistic units and drawing the reader's attention to the most conceptually significant parts of the text. (Ashurova, 2022)

Let us to consider as an example of stylistic information the fragment from English fiction that displays a convergence of stylistic devices in the opening paragraph of Charles Dickens's "A Tale of Two Cities":

"It was the best of times, it was the worst of times, it was the age of wisdom, it was the age of foolishness, it was the epoch of belief, it was the epoch of incredulity, it was the season of Light, it was the season of Darkness, it was the spring of hope, it was the winter of despair, we had everything before us, we had nothing before us, we

were all going direct to Heaven, we were all going direct the other way—in short, the period was so far like the present period, that some of its noisiest authorities insisted on its being received, for good or for evil, in the superlative degree of comparison only."

In this fragment, several stylistic devices are at play:

•**Parallelism:** The repetition of similar grammatical structures ("It was the...") creates a rhythm and reinforces the contrasts Dickens is highlighting. The rhythmic and repetitive structure created by parallelism and anaphora draws the reader in, making the passage memorable and engaging. This immediate engagement encourages the reader to continue with the text.

•**Antithesis:** The juxtaposition of opposing ideas ("best of times" vs. "worst of times," "age of wisdom" vs. "age of foolishness") emphasizes the contradictions and dualities of the era. The use of antithesis evokes strong emotions by presenting stark contrasts. Descriptions like "season of Light" versus "season of Darkness" and "spring of hope" versus "winter of despair" create a sense of drama and urgency, compelling the reader to feel the tension and complexity of the period.

•**Anaphora:** The repetition of "it was" at the beginning of successive clauses adds emphasis and a sense of inevitability to the statements being made.

•**Hyperbole:** Phrases like "the best of times" and "the worst of times" are examples of hyperbole, which exaggerate for effect. This use of hyperbole conveys the intensity of the contradictions and the dramatic nature of the period.

Together, these stylistic devices not only draw the reader in with their poetic and rhythmic qualities but also set the tone for the novel's exploration of the contrasts and conflicts of the period.

2. Pragmatic information

Each text is communicative and carries a specific message from the addresser to the addressee. The reader must independently extract information from the message and understand it, which leads to the formation of pragmatic relationships. These relationships can be intellectual and have a deep impact on the reader. The ability of a

text to cause a communicative effect and form a pragmatic relationship in the reader to what is being communicated is called the pragmatic aspect or pragmatic potential of the text. Pragmatic information is much broader, since it is aimed not only at evoking an emotional response in the reader, but also at motivating him to action (Ashurova, 2018).

An example of pragmatic information from an English-language work of fiction is the following excerpt from the novel "Moby Dick" by Herman Melville.

“The two knitting women increase his anxiety by gazing at him and all the other sailors with knowing unconcern. Their eerie looks suggest that they know what will happen (the men dying), yet don’t care.”

In the novel, the character Ishmael, the narrator, encounters two mysterious old women knitting as the whaling ship Pequod sets sail. The description of their "eerie looks" and "knowing unconcern" as they gaze at the sailors evokes the image of the Norns from Norse mythology.

This passage contains an allusion to the image of two knitting women from Scandinavian mythology - the Norns, who predetermines the fate of people. In Scandinavian mythology, the Norns are three women who control the destinies of gods and men. They spin the threads of life, determining birth, life, and death. Their gaze is penetrating and impassive, for they know the inevitable outcome of events, but do not interfere with the course of events.

In the description of the two knitting women in the passage, their "eerie" looks are emphasized, which indicate that they know about the impending death of the sailors, but treat it with indifference. This image refers to the archetypal image of the Norns, who impassively foretell fate. Thus, this allusion gives the described scene a mythological depth, endowing the two knitting women with a sinister knowledge of the inevitability of the upcoming tragic events.

In this case, the allusion to the Norns pursues the following pragmatic goals:

- To intensify the drama and anxiety of the narrative, to evoke a sense of anxiety and premonition of the impending tragedy in the reader.

- To emphasize the idea of the predetermination of human destinies, the impassive power of higher forces over the life and death of people.
- To create a sense of the presence of some mystical, supernatural force governing the events.

Thus, this allusion performs not only the function of a cultural referent, but also a pragmatic function - to influence the emotional perception and worldview of the reader, to enhance the drama and philosophical sound of the described scene.

Discussion.

Fictional texts have long captivated readers with their imaginative worlds, rich characterizations, and compelling narratives. While traditionally valued for their aesthetic and emotional impact, fictional texts also possess an inherent informativity that extends beyond mere entertainment. Fictional text is a means of transmitting information with elements of artistic fiction, emotional coloring and the creation of images. Taking the form of novels, poems, short stories, dramas and other textual genres, it can be realistic or fantastic. The purpose of this type of text is to create a specific atmosphere and evoke feelings and thoughts in the reader. Yu. M. Lotman (1972) believes that a fictional text is a model of the world and a message in the language of art, enriched with artistic codes and extra-textual connections. In it, natural language becomes a sign system, where ordinary linguistic units acquire new meaning and expressive capabilities, enriching the text with various shades and subtext (Lotman, 1972). Consequently, the originality of a fictional text is expressed in a unique combination of linguistic means, images, style, genre and theme, creating a unique atmosphere through the interaction of the author’s vision of the world and the internal conflicts of the characters. A fictional text is a special object of study.

Of course, one should agree with I.R. Galperin, who stood, in fact, at the origins of the development of text linguistics and argued that “one cannot talk about any object of study, in this case about a text, without naming its categories” (Galperin, 1981). According to modern research, textual categories are considered as textual qualities, units of analysis and field structure. However, the analysis shows that the

terminological apparatus in this area is still ambiguous, which is manifested in the variety of terms used to describe the text, such as categories, properties, text parameters, text features and categories, qualities and categories of the text. Some researchers note “the need to distinguish between text-forming categories and text properties” (Babenko & Kazarin, 2008).

Furthermore, I.R. Galperin differentiates three types of information in the text namely content-factual, content-conceptual and content-subtextual information. However, in the given article we are going to analyze stylistic and pragmatic types of fictional text informativity which is relatively new in text linguistics.

Therefore, a fictional text is a complex phenomenon where the interaction of information content, stylistics and pragmatics creates a unique aesthetic atmosphere and impact on the audience. A deep study of text categories helps to reveal the multi-layered nature of the text, its content and the purpose of conveying information, making it an object of attention for linguistic research.

Conclusion.

The exploration of the category of informativity in English fictional texts through a multidisciplinary and traditional approach including literary analysis, stylistic and pragmatic science has provided comprehensive understanding of the different types of information that present in fictional texts and their influence on the readers and society. Having finalized the research, it became clear that the category of informativity is inherent in all fictional texts and besides CFI, CCI, and CSI there are another two types of information such as stylistic and pragmatic information, which can be observed in the analyzed text fragments. By delving into fictional work such as "Moby Dick" we have witnessed how pragmatic information of fictional texts has highlighted their communicative power and ability to influence readers' perceptions, beliefs, and emotions.

Furthermore, the examination of stylistic elements such as imagery, emotiveness, and associative qualities has underscored the role of language in creating vivid worlds, evoking emotions, and enhancing reader engagement. Stylistic choices not only shape

the aesthetic qualities of a text but also serve to convey deeper layers of meaning, inviting readers to interpret and analyze the text beyond its surface narrative.

Having conducted the research, it is possible to draw a number of conclusions. The study of the category of informativity in English fictional text reveals a complex interplay of linguistic, stylistic, and pragmatic elements that contribute to the richness and depth of these narratives. A fictional text is a unique object of study, combining various linguistic means, images, styles, genres and themes to create a unique atmosphere and evoke feelings, emotions and thoughts in the reader. The study of the informativity of a text allows us to identify various types of information, such as content-factual, content-conceptual and content-subtextual information, which play a key role in the transmission of facts, ideas and individual author's code. Moreover, the examination of stylistic and pragmatic types of information in fictional texts, allows for a deeper understanding of their structure, content and impact on the reader. Stylistic information, expressed through the categories of imagery, emotiveness, evaluativeness, expressiveness, implicitness and associativity, enriches the text with various stylistic devices and creates the expressive component of the work, eliciting emotional responses, and facilitating interpersonal communication. Pragmatic information, in turn, is aimed at creating a communicative effect, evoking an emotional response in the reader and demanding action. Through careful attention to linguistic devices, tone, and narrative voice, authors craft narratives that resonate with readers on an emotional and intellectual level, fostering empathy, insight, and critical thinking.

Thanks to the informativity category one can find out in the fictional text five typological characteristics, each of them performs a certain function and is represented by corresponding indicators of various types. Through further exploration and analysis, we can continue to uncover new insights into the problem of informativity in English fictional texts and enrich our appreciation for the art of storytelling in all its complexity and diversity.

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